

Advancing Clinical Outcomes in Cervical Cancer: Investigating HDR Brachytherapy Dose Protocols

Shaik Athika¹, K. Sudhakar², Subbarajudu³

¹Junior Resident, Radition Oncology, NRI Medical College & General Hospital, Chinakakani – 522 503 Managalgi, Guntur (A.P.)

²Associate Professor, Radition Oncology, NRI Medical College & General Hospital, Chinakakani – 522 503 Managalgi, Guntur (A.P.)

³Medical physinist, Radition Oncology, NRI Medical College & General Hospital, Chinakakani – 522 503 Managalgi, Guntur (A.P.)

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 25-10-2024

Corresponding Author: K. Sudhakar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Cervical cancer (CC) is the 4th most prevalent cancer among women in this global. Chronic HPV infections which mainly strains 16 and 18, raise cervical cancer risks, which requires showing from the age of 21. The treatment choices variety from cryotherapy in the early stages to brachytherapy and high-dose radiation therapy (HDRBT) in the final stages. These actions allow for precision tumor directing with least experience to healthy tissue, which finally recovers survival rates.

Aim and objectives: The goal of this study is to explore the clinical effectiveness and toxicity of two HDR brachytherapy dose treatments for cervical cancer therapy find the best balance between tumor control and side effects.

Method: This 24-month study at NRI Medical College's Department of Radiation Oncology examined two HDR brachytherapy routines for cervical cancer patients. Patients had simultaneous chemotherapy, external beam radiation treatment (EBRT), and one of two high-dose rate (HDR) dosage fractional process. Tumor control and toxicity were determined by clinical and imaging assessments. In addition, these results were classified with RECIST criteria, and toxicities were categorized using CTCAE guidelines.

Result: The research assessed two high-dose rate brachytherapy protocols (Arm A:5.5 Gy; Arm B: 7 Gy) for cervical cancer. Both arms reached comparable local control rates (90%), with Arm A showing a marginal advantage in disease-free survival (100% vs. 95%). Arm B showed high acute bladder and rectal toxicity. Biologically effective doses (BED) were high in Arm B, resulting in heightened toxicity.

Conclusion: This study concluded that Arm A has shown a slightly higher disease-free survival (DFS) rate (100%) compared to Arm B (95%), indicating a potential advantage in preventing disease recurrence.

Keywords: Cervical cancer, HDRBT, EBRT, tumours, chemotherapy, DFS.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Cervical cancer (CC) is still one of the major concerns for gynaecologic cancers worldwide. Currently, it ranks as the 14th most common cancer and is placed as the 4th most frequent type among females around the world [1]. HPV prevalence is significantly the highest in the age range of under 25 years while CC mortality tends to peak in women aged 40 to 50 years [1].

Radiation plays a predominant role in the management of carcinoma cervix mainly EBRT and Brachytherapy. Brachytherapy (BT) plays a crucial role in the management of CC. The radiation dose goes directly to the tumour with minimal exposure to healthy tissues around it. This modality is particularly useful in the locally advanced situation, which permits direct access to

targeted dose escalation, thus improving patient outcomes. Advances such as image-guided adaptive techniques now enhance local tumour control and survival in BT.

Because brachytherapy is less toxic and more effective than other forms of radiotherapy, it has remained one of the most important forms in management of advanced CC [7,8].

High-Dose Rate (HDR) BT plays a major role in treatment for locally advanced CC, for optimal control of outcome as it delivers targeted, high doses of radiation to the tumour. The American BT Society recommends an infield tumour dose in the range of 80-90 Gy based on tumour size during treatment [9]. Success relies heavily on careful

selection and placement of applicators, supported by advanced imaging in MRI or CT to guide precise treatment planning and individualized dosimetry with each session. HDRBT offers excellent local control of the tumour and survival benefits and therefore provides a foundational approach in CC management [9]. Fractionation schedules around 9 Gy per session over two to five sessions have proven to be promising. The HDRBT dose rates should be 0.50 to 0.65 Gy per hour to allow precise delivery in intracavitary BT [9].

Methodology

The study was conducted in the Department of Radiation Oncology at NRI Medical College & General Hospital. This institution is a tertiary care centre with a dedicated oncology unit, equipped with state-of-the-art facilities for external beam radiation therapy (EBRT) and high-dose-rate (HDR) intracavitary brachytherapy. The study spanned a period of 24 months, from January 2021 to December 2022. This study was conducted using a two different dose fractionation regimens of high-dose-rate (HDR) intracavitary brachytherapy in patients diagnosed with carcinoma of the cervix. The study was carried out in the Department of Radiation Oncology and included both prospective and retrospective data from eligible participants. The primary objectives of the study were to assess local tumour control rates and the incidence of treatment-related toxicities during a follow-up period of three months. All participants received standard treatment protocols, including concurrent chemotherapy and external beam radiation therapy (EBRT) alongside HDR brachytherapy.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

- The inclusion criteria: 18 and 60 years of age,
- carcinoma cervix staged IA to IIIB according to the 2018 FIGO
- (ECOG) performance status of 1 or 2
- suitable for concurrent chemotherapy and radiation therapy.
- Histologically confirmed cervical cancer and provided informed consent for study participation.

Exclusion criteria

- over 60 years of age or under 18,
- stage IV cervical cancer,
- an ECOG performance status of 3 or higher
- A history of previous radiation therapy.
- Those with contraindications to brachytherapy or chemotherapy or who declined to give informed consent were also excluded from the study.

Procedure: Eligible patients were screened for the study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria and written consent was obtained. A detailed

baseline evaluation which involved a detailed history, clinical examination, and imaging studies was done. Cancer staging was performed using the FIGO 2018 system. Patients who met the study criteria were randomly assigned to two interventional arms. In Arm A, patients received 5.5 Gy in 4 fractions given once a week for three weeks. In Arm B, patients received 7 Gy in three fractions, given ten days apart. All patients received concurrent chemotherapy with weekly 40 mg/m² cisplatin and external beam radiotherapy (EBRT) with a total dose of 50 Gy delivered in 25 fractions, five times a week for five weeks. HDR brachytherapy was commenced after the completion of 22 fractions of EBRT and was performed using modified Fletcher Suit applicators. This was done after dragging the cervix with Hegar's dilator, sounded the uterine cavity, and pairs of intrauterine tandems and ovoids were placed according to the architecture of the anatomy. Betadine-soaked gauze was utilized to fix the applicator and push away surrounding organs like the bladder and rectum.

A CT scan of the pelvis was acquired after applicator placement to facilitate treatment planning with the Varian Brachy Vision System. Point A (2 cm lateral and 2 cm above the cervical os) was targeted for the prescribed dose and the dose limit of the bladder and rectum was adhered according to the ICRU Report 38. Dose adjustment was undertaken to facilitate complete coverage of the cancerous area while limiting the radiation to the uninfected tissues. The Varian Gamma Med Plus remote after loading system was used for the treatment sessions. All patients were assessed on a weekly basis throughout the period of treatment for the purpose of detecting any acute toxicities using common terminology criteria for adverse Events (CTCAE) version 4.0, outpatient treatment was evaluated one month and three months after completion of treatment so as to determine sexuality as well as toxicity of the tumour. Structure of the tumour was evaluated clinically and on imaging according to the RECIST 1.0 and the findings were recorded as complete response (CR), partial response (PR), progressive disease (PD), or stable disease (SD). A profile of the safety of both treatment regimens was constructed by grading and recording toxicities during treatment and follow up. No detail was spared within each finding considering the future use for statistical analysis.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis for this study was performed using a combination of descriptive and comparative statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, including measures such as mean, median, standard deviation, and frequency distributions, were employed to summarise patient demographic data and treatment outcomes.

Comparative analyses, including t-tests and chi-square tests, were utilised to examine differences in clinical outcomes and toxicities between the two treatment arms. Survival analyses were performed to determine disease-free survival rates at three months, and p-values of <0.05 were considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were conducted using appropriate software to ensure accuracy and reproducibility.

Results

The mean age of patients in Arm A was 43 years (SD 6.96), compared to 45 years (SD 7.12) in Arm B. Although there was a slight difference in the age distribution, with more patients in the 31–40 age range in Arm B, this was not statistically significant ($p=0.25$). Regarding residence, a notable majority of participants in both arms were from rural areas, with 85% in Arm A and 95% in Arm B. The urban population was minimal in both groups, and the difference in residence between the arms did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.12$). The ECOG performance status, which assesses the

patients' functional ability, showed that most patients in both arms were classified as Grade 1, accounting for 80% of participants in Arm A and 85% in Arm B. This similarity between the groups was not statistically significant ($p=0.67$). Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) was the predominant type in both arms. Other subtypes, such as well-differentiated SCC and adenocarcinoma, were observed in lower frequencies across both groups. The distribution of these subtypes showed no significant difference between the arms ($p=0.42$).

Finally, with respect to FIGO staging, Stage IIB was the most commonly observed stage in both treatment arms, with 55% of patients in Arm A and 60% in Arm B. Stages IIA, IIIA, and IIIB were less common, and the overall distribution of FIGO stages was similar between the arms, with no statistically significant difference ($p=0.31$). These results suggest that the two arms were well-balanced in terms of demographic and clinical characteristics, with no significant disparities across the evaluated parameters.

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of the patients in each arm and their significances

Characteristic	Arm A (n=20)	Arm B (n=20)	P-Value
Age (years)			
31–40	3	5	0.25
41–50	10	6	
51–60	7	9	
Mean Age (SD)	43 (6.96)	45 (7.12)	
Residence			
Rural	17	19	0.12
Urban	3	1	
ECOG Performance Status			
Grade 1	16	17	0.67
Grade 2	4	3	
Histological Subtype			
Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC)	3	3	0.42
Well-Differentiated SCC (WD SCC)	1	3	
Moderately Differentiated SCC (MD SCC)	13	11	
Poorly Differentiated SCC (PD SCC)	2	1	
Adenocarcinoma	1	1	
Adenosquamous	0	1	
FIGO Stage			
IIA	1	4	0.31
IIB	11	12	
IIIA	4	2	
IIIB	4	6	

Figure 2 compares the local control rate and disease-free survival rate for patients treated with 5.5 Gy (Arm A) and 7 Gy (Arm B). Both arms achieved an identical local control rate of 90%, indicating comparable efficacy in controlling tumour growth at the treatment site.

However, differences were observed in the disease-free survival (DFS) rates. Arm A demonstrated a 100% DFS rate, indicating all patients were free

from disease recurrence during the follow-up period. In contrast, Arm B showed a slightly lower DFS rate of 95%, suggesting that a small proportion of patients in this group experienced disease recurrence or progression. These findings highlight that while both regimens are equally effective in local control, Arm A might offer a marginal advantage in terms of maintaining disease-free survival.

Figure 2: Local control and disease-free survival in patients of each arm

Table 3 outlines the acute bladder and rectal adverse events experienced by patients in Arm A and Arm B. Among bladder-related events, dysuria was reported in 50% of patients in Arm A and 60% in Arm B, indicating a slightly higher occurrence in the latter group. Haematuria, a less frequent adverse event, occurred in 5% of patients in Arm A and 10% in Arm B. Similarly, an increased frequency of urination was reported in 40% of Arm A and 50% of ArmB patients. These results suggest

that bladder-related toxicities were more common in Arm B.

Rectal adverse events also displayed higher frequencies in Arm B. Diarrhoea was observed in 40% of Arm A patients and 50% in Arm B. Rectal bleeding, which occurred less frequently, was noted in 10% of patients in Arm A and 20% in Arm B. Proctitis was reported in 30% of Arm A patients, compared to 40% in Arm B. These findings indicate a higher prevalence of rectal toxicity in Arm B compared to Arm A.

Table 3: Adverse Events of the patients in each group

Acute Bladder Adverse Events		
Adverse Events	Arm A (n=20)	Arm B (n=20)
Dysuria	50%	60%
Haematuria	5%	10%
Increased Frequency	40%	50%
Acute Rectal Adverse Events		
Adverse Events	Arm A (n=20)	Arm B (n=20)
Diarrhoea	40%	50%
Rectal Bleeding	10%	20%
Proctitis	30%	40%

Table 4 compares the biologically effective doses (BED) for the tumour, bladder, and rectum between the two treatment arms. The tumour BED was slightly higher in Arm B at 95.7 Gy, compared to 94.1 Gy in Arm A, reflecting a marginally higher radiation dose delivered to the tumour in Arm B. Bladder BED was also higher in Arm B, measuring 153.3 Gy compared to 145.6 Gy in Arm A, indicating a greater exposure of the bladder to

radiation in Arm B. Similarly, the rectum BED in Arm B was 150.5 Gy, exceeding the 140.2 Gy observed in Arm A. These results highlight that while Arm B delivers a slightly higher effective dose to the tumour, it also increases radiation exposure to the bladder and rectum, potentially contributing to the greater prevalence of acute toxicities in this group.

Table 4: Total Biologically Effective Dose (BED)

Parameter	Arm A (5.5 Gy)	Arm B (7 Gy)
Tumour BED (Gy)	94.1	95.7
Bladder BED (Gy)	145.6	153.3
Rectum BED (Gy)	140.2	150.5

Discussion

Balaraj et al. (2024) conducted a retrospective study in the UAE that evaluated the effectiveness of HDRBT in CC patients. Overall survival at 12 months was significantly more in the HDRBT cohort compared with the non-BT group ($p=0.0035$). Disease progression was observed in 37.88% in the total cohort, while 86.68% of patients survived to the last follow-up. This ultimately led to an improvement in the survival outcome from HDRBT and indicates the point at which closer access, standard protocols, and minimizing unnecessary complications would be necessary to assure a more effective outcome [10].

Patel et al. (2005) reported an experience using HDRBT to treat Stage I-III CC. Group 1 patients received the combination of external beam radiotherapy and HDRBT, constituting 18 patients. Group 2 consisted of 95 patients, who received only external beam radiotherapy. The outcome was found at 5-year actuarial local control and disease-free survival rates at 74.5% and 62%, respectively. HDRBT at 9 Gy/fraction proved to be safe and effective with good local control with minimal toxicity [11].

Kim et al. (2010) conducted a study to assess the dosimetric outcomes of 3D image-guided HDRBT in the treatment of CC. A total of thirty-two patients who had stage IA2-IIIB CC were treated with HDRBT with five fractions at prescription levels of 5.0-6.0 Gy per fraction. The study proved D90 for HRCTV significantly more considerable than the dose to Point A, (83.2 ± 4.3 Gy) versus (78.6 ± 4.4 Gy, $p < 0.0001$). Authors concluded that transition from the traditional 2D point dose dosimetry to the 3D will offer better dose coverage [12].

Lee and Viswanathan (2012) conducted research aimed at identifying predictors of severe complications and rectal toxicity in women receiving treatment for gynaecologic cancers through HDRBT. The median total dose was 72 Gy, while in external beam radiotherapy, the dose was 45 Gy and the remainder 24 Gy in BT. It was observed that D2cc for the rectum was one of the key predictors. A higher D2cc was related to increased risk for rectal toxicity, where 10% risk of grade 2-4 rectal toxicity was seen at 61.8 Gy. The author concluded that BT presented with manageable toxicity and that the rectal D2cc well predicted late complications [13].

With MRI and CT imaging, optimal BT planning and dosimetry are now complemented. The exact targeting of a tumour down to the least exposure to surrounding healthy tissue is now possible, enabled by the combination of 3D imaging with adaptive BT, which further optimizes treatment efficacy with minimum adverse effects through tailoring the

plan following the specific features of both the tumour and patient anatomy. Such advanced technologies bring about great improvements in the outcomes and precision of BT, argue studies [14-16].

HDRBT has several challenges, one of which is the complicated process of selecting and inserting the appropriate applicator. Therefore, the right selection of appropriator applicator ensures correct dose distribution, and the coverage of the tumour [17]. Moreover, on account of the image-guided BT, technical and logistical complexities are involved. Highly complex imaging and precise treatment planning are required for this kind of therapeutic approach coupled with rigorous safety and infection control, which cannot be attained in many healthcare systems. Moreover, there is also a fear of ionizing radiation causing toxicity to the surrounding healthy tissues, which is an increasing issue, although advanced imaging techniques allow tumours to be targeted much more precisely and with less collateral damage to the surrounding tissues [17-19].

Future directions with HDRBT for CC patients investigate methods for higher dose escalation and the optimization of treatment. Current studies involve the use of 3D imaging to further enhance dosimetry using after loading applicators to help maximize the target volume coverage while minimizing exposure to the adjacent organs. Combination HDR BT with immunotherapy or chemotherapy is another promising approach used to augment the efficacy of the treatment. Secondly, emphasis on patient-specific protocols: one has maximal applicator variability with respect to anatomy and uses detailed imaging for maximizing tumour targeting and minimizing normal tissue use, aiming at an improved overall treatment outcome [20,10].

Conclusion

This study observed that advanced dose fractionation regimens, such as the low dose rate of 5.5 Gy, achieved similar control rates compared to higher dose fractions of 7 Gy. Additionally, the lower dose rate fractionated regimens showed slightly better outcomes in terms of local control, disease-free survival (DFS), and had lower toxicity profiles when compared to the higher dose fractions. However, the study emphasizes the need for a longer follow-up period to definitively establish the superiority of lower fractionation regimens.

References

1. Fowler, J. R., Maani, E. V., Dunton, C. J., Gasalberti, D. P., & Jack, B. W. Cervical cancer. In StatPearls. StatPearls Publishing, 2024.
2. Yao, H., Yan, C., Qiumin, H., Li, Z., Jiao, A., Xin, L., & Hong, L. Epidemiological trends

- and attributable risk burden of cervical cancer: An observational study from 1990 to 2019. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*, 2022;3356431.
3. Farghaly, H., Bourgeois, D., Houser, P. M., Padmanabhan, V., Lage, J. M., & Hoda, R. S. Routine vaginal Pap test is not useful in women status-post hysterectomy for benign disease. *Diagnostic Cytopathology*, 2006;34(9):640–643.
 4. Burness, J. V., Schroeder, J. M., & Warren, J. B. Cervical colposcopy: Indications and risk assessment. *American Family Physician*, 2020;102(1):39–48.
 5. Mirpour, S., Mhlanga, J. C., Logeswaran, P., Russo, G., Mercier, G., & Subramaniam, R. M. The role of PET/CT in the management of cervical cancer. *AJR. American Journal of Roentgenology*, 2013;201(2):W192-205.
 6. Senol, T., Polat, M., Ozkaya, E., & Karateke, A. Comparison of two step LEEP and cold conisation for cervical intraepithelial lesions to decrease positive surgical margins. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention: APJCP*, 2016;17(7):3317–3320.
 7. Holschneider, C. H., Petereit, D. G., Chu, C., Hsu, I.-C., Ioffe, Y. J., Klopp, A. H., Pothuri, B., Chen, L.-M., & Yashar, C. Brachytherapy: A critical component of primary radiation therapy for cervical cancer: From the Society of Gynecologic Oncology (SGO) and the American Brachytherapy Society (ABS). *Gynecologic Oncology*, 2019;152(3):540–547.
 8. Sturdza, A. E., & Knoth, J. Image-guided brachytherapy in cervical cancer including fractionation. *International Journal of Gynecological Cancer: Official Journal of the International Gynecological Cancer Society*, 2022;32(3):273–280.
 9. Viswanathan, A. N., Beriwal, S., De Los Santos, J. F., Demanes, D. J., Gaffney, D., Hansen, J., Jones, E., Kirisits, C., Thomadsen, B., Erickson, B., & American Brachytherapy Society. American Brachytherapy Society consensus guidelines for locally advanced carcinoma of the cervix. Part II: high-dose-rate brachytherapy. *Brachytherapy*, 2012;11(1):47–52.
 10. Balaraj, K., Bin Sumaida, A., AlKaabi, K., & Shanbhag, N. M. High-dose-rate brachytherapy in cervical and endometrial cancer patients: A retrospective study from a tertiary cancer center in the UAE. *Cureus*, 2024;16(8):e66702.
 11. Patel, F. D., Rai, B., Mallick, I., & Sharma, S. C. High-dose-rate brachytherapy in uterine cervical carcinoma. *International Journal of Radiation Oncology, Biology, Physics*, 2005;62(1):125–130.
 12. Kim, H., Beriwal, S., Houser, C., & Huq, M. S. Dosimetric analysis of 3D image-guided HDR brachytherapy planning for the treatment of cervical cancer: is point A-based dose prescription still valid in image-guided brachytherapy? *Medical Dosimetry: Official Journal of the American Association of Medical Dosimetrists*, 2010;36(2):166–170.
 13. Lee, L. J., & Viswanathan, A. N. Predictors of toxicity after image-guided high-dose-rate interstitial brachytherapy for gynecologic cancer. *International Journal of Radiation Oncology, Biology, Physics*, 2012;84(5):1192–1197.
 14. Nag, S., Erickson, B., Thomadsen, B., Orton, C., Demanes, J. D., & Petereit, D. The American Brachytherapy Society recommendations for high-dose-rate brachytherapy for carcinoma of the cervix. *International Journal of Radiation Oncology, Biology, Physics*, 2000;48(1): 201–211.
 15. Ghosh, S., Rao, P. B., & Kotne, S. High dose rate brachytherapy in two 9 Gy fractions in the treatment of locally advanced cervical cancer - a south Indian institutional experience. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention: APJCP*, 2015;16(16):7167–7170.
 16. Gagrani, V., Kabara, J., Shukla, A., Rathore, N. K., Rajpurohit, V. S., Jangid, P. K., & Manna, S. A comparative study between two different dose fractionation schedules of cobalt-60-based HDR intracavitary brachytherapy in carcinoma cervix stages IIB-IIIC1. *Journal of Cancer Research and Therapeutics*, 2024;20(5):1551–1556.
 17. Vargo, J. A., & Beriwal, S. Image-based brachytherapy for cervical cancer. *World Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 2014;5(5):921–930.
 18. Altioek, E., Aksoy, F., Perk, Y., Taylan, F., Kim, P. W., Ilkkan, B., Asal, G. T., Goldbach-Mansky, R., & Sanal, O. A novel mutation in the interleukin-1 receptor antagonist associated with intrauterine disease onset. *Clinical Immunology (Orlando, Fla.)*, 2012;145(1):77–81.
 19. Tharmalingam, H., Alonzi, R., & Hoskin, P. J. The role of magnetic resonance imaging in brachytherapy. *Clinical Oncology (Royal College of Radiologists (Great Britain))*, 2018;30(11):728–736.
 20. Fumagalli, I., Haie-Méder, C., & Chargari, C. 3D brachytherapy for cervical cancer: New optimization ways. *Cancer Radiotherapie: Journal de La Societe Francaise de Radiotherapie Oncologique*, 2018;22(4):345–351.